

Abstract

Detection of symptoms of depression using signal processing techniques and machine learning from voice analysis as a biomarker

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Abstract: Depression is a mental disorder that affects thousands of people regardless of gender or age. Its diagnosis usually includes completing self-report questionnaires which, unfortunately, can be easily manipulated by the patients in order to avoid a possible diagnosis. Further, a personal interview with a mental health professional, while more accurate, can be very time-consuming. There is still no biomarker for the diagnosis of depression, however, the patient's voice has been recently reported as an encouraging possible one. In this work we attempt to detect symptoms of depression based on recordings of audio in undergraduate students in order to develop a robust tool that can support mental health experts and clinicians in the diagnosis of depression. Machine learning techniques are used to find patterns based on the characteristics extracted from the audio recordings. The implementation of a genetic algorithm is used with the intention of finding the best configuration of the hyperparameters of the artificial intelligence models used. While the results are still preliminary, they appear to be encouraging in terms of eventually recognizing voice as a biomarker for depression.

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Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

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References

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